

Legacy in Hematology and Cancer Immunology: An Interview with Prof. Dr. Emin Kansu

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Abstract—This interview with Prof. Dr. Emin Kansu explores his remarkable career in hematology and cancer immunology, highlighting his role in the establishment of the Hacettepe Cancer Institute. Prof. Dr. Kansu reflects on his academic journey from Hacettepe University to the United States, where he specialized in blood diseases and immunology, and his return to Turkey to contribute to the country's medical advancements. The discussion includes the challenges of academic mentorship, the evolution of medical research in Turkey, and the future prospects of fields such as bioinformatics, genomic medicine, and stem cell research. Prof. Dr. Kansu also shares his insights on the ethical considerations surrounding the use of artificial intelligence in medicine, highlighting the need for ongoing dialogue and regulation in this rapidly advancing field.

Keywords—Hematology, Cancer Immunology, Hacettepe University, Medical ethics, Medicine in Turkey

I. INTRODUCTION

Prof. Dr. Emin Kansu's contributions to the fields of hematology and cancer immunology have left an indelible mark on medical research and education in Turkey. A graduate of Hacettepe University Faculty of Medicine, Prof. Dr. Kansu pursued advanced training in the United States, where he specialized in internal medicine, hematology, and immunology. Upon his return to Turkey, he played a critical role in establishing the Hacettepe University Cancer Institute, a pioneering institution that has become a cornerstone for cancer treatment and research in the country.

Throughout his career, Prof. Dr. Kansu has been deeply committed to academic mentorship, guiding countless students and young researchers. His efforts have significantly contributed to the development of medical education and research infrastructure in Turkey. In this interview, Prof. Dr. Kansu shares his insights on the evolution of medical research, the challenges and opportunities in academic mentorship, and the ethical considerations surrounding emerging technologies like artificial intelligence in medicine.

As a recipient of prestigious awards, including the TÜBİTAK Science Award, Prof. Dr. Kansu's reflections provide valuable perspectives on the current state and future directions of medical research in Turkey and beyond. This conversation offers an opportunity to gain a deeper understanding of the experiences and vision of one of Turkey's leading medical researchers.

II. COULD YOU INTRODUCE YOURSELF?

I graduated from Hacettepe University Faculty of Medicine in 1970. Shortly after, I went to the United States for specialization training and residency. I spent a year working as an intern there and completed my residency. After completing my post-graduate education in the U.S., I returned to Hacettepe University in 1980. During my time in the U.S., I completed training in internal medicine, followed by further training in hematology and immunology.

Upon my return to Hacettepe, I began advancing in academia—first becoming an associate professor and later a full professor. It was during this period that we conceived the idea of establishing a Cancer Institute at Hacettepe University, an institution that would focus on both the prevention, treatment, and research of cancer, a significant need for both the university and Turkey at the time. Alongside my colleagues, we successfully founded the Hacettepe University Cancer Institute, which operates as a major institution on campus. With Professors Dinçer Firat, Namık Çevik, and Şevket Ruacan I also played a key role in its foundation and the training of its faculty members. We established clinical departments within the institute, including medical and pediatric oncology, preventive radiation oncology, nuclear medicine and tumor pathology. By 2003, the Cancer Institute became fully operational with its inpatient and outpatient services.

Throughout this process, we received tremendous support from many people, notably the late Mr. Süleyman Demirel President of the Turkish Republic at the time, who appreciated the necessity of this Institute and provided crucial assistance. The university administration was also highly supportive, and many of my students who were trained in the Cancer Institute have now become professors, specializing in various fields. Many of them spent two or three years in the U.S. before returning, and today, they are leading authorities in their respective areas.

I was particularly involved in the establishment of cancer research and basic oncology and even spent two years abroad to help set up the bone marrow transplant unit. Today, we can

Prof. Dr. Emin Kansu

proudly say that the Hacettepe University Cancer Institute serves as a reference center in Turkey for both pediatric and medical oncology. This has been a significant part of my academic life, and I am very happy with what we've achieved.

I retired in 2014 due to my age and looking back, I can say that we have made significant contributions to medicine, hematology, oncology, pathology, and academics in Turkey. The Institute now receives around 4,000 new cancer patients every year, providing diagnoses and treatment plans for both children and adults and offering an invaluable service. Every unit in the country consults with this Institute and refers patients here for diagnosis and treatment. During my time there, my work was purely academic; I didn't open a private practice. I focused on education, research, and patient care within the Cancer Institute.

In state universities, the mandatory retirement age is 67, while in private universities like Koç, you can work beyond 70, as far as I know. Although my days now are less intense than before after retiring, I'm staying academically active by visiting national universities, giving lectures, at Jefferson Medical College, reviewing projects, and evaluating award applications.

III. YOUR WORK IN HEMATOLOGY AND CANCER IMMUNOLOGY IS QUITE REMARKABLE. WHAT SPECIFIC TOPIC IN THESE FIELDS EXCITES YOU THE MOST AND KEEPS YOU ENGAGED IN YOUR RESEARCH?

I enjoyed every aspect of my work. As academics, we all specialize in a particular field. We can't afford to be scattered, saying, "I'll look into this, and I'll look into that," especially in medicine. You need to receive training and become an expert in a single area. It's similar to engineering, where you must specialize in a specific field; it's impossible to know everything. I was particularly interested in blood diseases and the immune system problems that arise from them. These two issues are crucial mechanisms in the development of cancer.

You might ask, for example, "Why didn't you focus on brain tumors?" That could have been an option, of course. However, since my education in the U.S. was focused on blood diseases, I naturally entered this field. But it's tough to pick just one area among the ones I've worked on, especially when you enjoy what you do. My research primarily focused on blood production. I explored the problems that occur in blood production from the bone marrow, how blood is produced normally, and how it is produced under disease conditions. In medical terms, we call this phenomenon 'Hematopoiesis'. This is still not fully understood; we haven't completely unraveled the mechanisms of its control but we're working on it and have made significant progress.

For example, one of my distinguished world-famous mentors in the U.S. discovered a hormone that influences this process—a hormone called Erythropoietin, which is secreted by the kidneys. It travels to the bone marrow and controls the production of red blood cells. I was very much interested in this process and spent four or five years studying it. I researched the mechanisms by which this hormone affects the bone marrow, how it initiates blood production, and its biological properties, and I published several papers on this topic.

Back then immunology was just beginning to gain recognition—this was around 1978-79. This new field was generating a lot of excitement, and alongside blood production, I became very interested in it as well. After all, immune cells are produced during the blood production process. This was a very enjoyable research journey for me, and when I returned to Turkey, I assisted students with their theses and research projects on this subject.

IV. WHILE YOU WERE A STUDENT AT HACETTEPE UNIVERSITY FACULTY OF MEDICINE, WAS THERE A SPECIFIC EVENT OR MOMENT THAT DIRECTED YOU TOWARD SUCH A SUCCESSFUL ACADEMIC CAREER? DURING THIS PERIOD, DID YOU HAVE A MENTOR OR ROLE MODEL WHO INSPIRED YOU?

It's impossible to pinpoint a single event; anyone who claims otherwise is just telling a tale. In university education, it's a group of professors who guide you; you can't just pick one because they all complement each other's teachings. We were fortunate at Hacettepe because the university was founded in 1964, and we were its first students. As the first students, we were led by Professor İhsan Doğramacı, who founded the Hacettepe University. Foreseeing the establishment of this faculty, he had sent many young academics to the United States in the mid-1950s. When these

individuals returned, they formed the academic staff of our university, even before becoming associate professors. They were working with great enthusiasm, having just returned, the faculty was brand new, the course topics were freshly developed, and the students were new as well, so they provided us with an excellent education. Our class size was also small, just 64 students. This was an ideal number at the time, allowing the professors to pay close attention to each of us, get to know us well, identify any deficiencies that might arise, and address them, ultimately giving us an outstanding medical education over six years.

Of course, as students, we observed our professors—what they were teaching, which areas they emphasized, and how they conducted their lectures. Since they had returned from America, they educated us according to the American medical education model of 1968. Because of these conditions, it's tough to single out one person or event. As we entered our final year, in 1969-70, during our last year as interns, working like doctors before officially becoming doctors, our professors encouraged us to continue our education in the United States. Not everyone went, of course, but 20-25 of us did, having seen how our professors had been trained there and how deeply it had impacted them. We took the American exams of that time, like the ECFMG, and scored high marks. We graduated in 1970 and went to the U.S. for further education. However, the foundation of our academic education was still laid at Hacettepe.

Of course, not all graduates from our term became academics; some worked in hospitals, and others opened private practices. Not everyone is required to be an academic; it's a profession that requires dedication. It requires a commitment to student education, teaching, and feeling responsible for a student's learning, which is why I don't intend to criticize those who don't pursue academia. However, many of our classmates who graduated with us continued as academics. In this regard, our professors at Hacettepe provided mentorship for us, and by the 1970s, Hacettepe had started to establish itself as a model for other universities in the country. However, I should mention Professors Şeref Zileli and Faruk Özer as my distinguished mentors who convinced me to receive my post-graduate training in internal medicine and hematology.

V. AFTER GRADUATING, YOU CONTINUED YOUR EDUCATION AND RESEARCH AT THOMAS JEFFERSON UNIVERSITY. WHAT WAS IT LIKE FOR YOU TO WORK ABROAD AT A YOUNG AGE?

WHAT DIFFERENCES DID YOU OBSERVE BETWEEN THE MEDICAL FIELD IN TURKEY AND ABROAD? WHAT ARE YOUR THOUGHTS ON THE ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF THESE DIFFERENCES?

That's a difficult question. People might say "If America excels in science, why can't we?". Well, we can't. How many gold medals did the U.S. win in the Olympics? Forty, the same as China. We can't compare ourselves to a country like that. Their athletes have been training for years, extensively preparing physically before every competition. It's a country with a population of 336 million, built on a very disciplined and education-oriented culture that's built on decades of hard work and progress, and apart from China, right now, no other

Hacettepe University Cancer Institute, 2006

country has that. China, of course, isn't as open to the world, but it's still able to compete with the U.S. I won't compare Turkey to America; that would be a mistaken endeavor. But I'd rather tell you why I decided to come back to Turkey. I experienced America, understood all its aspects during my 12 years there, and then decided to return. When I decided to return my boss and my colleagues said, "Don't go back," but I insisted saying "No, I'm going back. I won't stay in America." I love the US, but I rejected becoming American. I understand and appreciate the United States, but I felt that I was obligated to bring back what I learned back to Turkey and to the Turkish students. When my professor asked me why I was returning, I said, "I come from a middle-class, civil-servant family. And even though my family wasn't wealthy they still managed to have me educated at TED Ankara College, which was expensive for families even back then. They sacrificed from themselves, even cut on their meals, but they still managed to have me and my sibling educated. When I was accepted to Hacettepe Medical School and studied there for six years I truly realized how much Turkey had invested in my education. I could stay in the US, but why would I? An American student has lots of resources, he can find 300-500 professors like me, but a Turkish student can't. If I can provide this education to Turkish students and give back to them what I had received, I could be of more use." My department head respected that greatly.

Students often ask me, "Should I go to America and stay there?" "I can't answer that question. You should go to America; as a computer engineer, you should see the work they're doing and stay there for as long you want. However, the decision, whether to stay or to return, is a personal one that no professor can make this decision for you. You're at UCLA right now and might be thinking "I've learned everything I set off to learn and got what I needed from here, I'm going back to Turkey." That's a very respectable choice but no one can say anything against you either if you choose to stay. We personally chose not to stay. But we still attend conferences, and teach periodically at U.S. universities, and that's enough for us. Seeing a student listen to you attentively, focused on what you're passionately explaining, is a wonderful thing. If I or your professors at Koç University had wanted to stay in America, we could have done so. Your professors at Koç are highly valued; I know them and the internal structure of the university well because I worked there. The medical school is excellent with a faculty comprising of very prominent names

and they didn't stay. Ultimately they chose to educate the students at Koç University and make a meaningful impact on their lives because that was what made them happy with their contributions and satisfied with their careers.

VI. HOW DID YOU FEEL WHEN YOU WON THE TÜBİTAK (THE SCIENTIFIC AND TECHNOLOGICAL RESEARCH COUNCIL OF TÜRKİYE) SCIENCE AWARD? HOW DID THIS AWARD IMPACT YOUR SCIENTIFIC WORK?

We obviously don't work for the sake of winning awards; I've never worked with the goal of receiving an award. Some people may be more eager about it, but that's not really the right approach to have. The work you do might be noticed and appreciated by some professors and faculty members, and they may decide to give you an award. Naturally, you feel happy when your work is recognized; it's satisfying to know that your efforts are appreciated, and it can be demoralizing if they aren't. If I see someone doing good work but not being recognized, I make sure to bring it to the attention of the relevant people, who then evaluate the person's work independently. But as I said, we don't work for awards. The TÜBİTAK Science Award is the highest scientific award in Turkey; winning it gives us an extra drive, a motivation to ask ourselves, "Can I do even more research, be even better?" Awards provide motivation; people who receive them continue their work with renewed energy. I received the TÜBİTAK Encouragement Award in 1979 and the TÜBİTAK Science Award in 1997. At that time, our professors evaluated our work and found it deserving; but, even if I hadn't won the award, I would have continued working.

VII. YOU'VE SERVED UNDER THE UMBRELLA OF TÜBA (THE TURKISH ACADEMY OF SCIENCES) FOR MANY YEARS. BASED ON YOUR EXPERIENCES DURING THIS TIME, WHAT KIND OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND INFRASTRUCTURE IMPROVEMENTS DO YOU BELIEVE SHOULD BE MADE TO MORE EFFECTIVELY SUPPORT AND ADVANCE SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH IN TURKEY? IN YOUR OPINION, WHICH AREAS SHOULD BE PRIORITIZED?

I'm the first full member of TÜBA, and currently, I'm an honorary member. I still visit universities across Turkey and this year, I'll be visiting places like Bitlis University, Süleyman Demirel University, and 9 Eylül University. In my visits I meet with rectors, deans, and students, trying to understand how they are doing. For example, I visited Kahramanmaraş University, and you have to understand that there's a significant difference between the conditions there and 9 Eylül University. The professors at universities like Kahramanmaraş University only work there for a while and some of them may move on to other universities. While I intend to visit more universities in Eastern and Southeastern Anatolia, I see that the biggest issue in these universities is the lack of mentors and experienced professors. How can science progress without mentors- people who guide and educate you? At Koç University you have an abundance of people who are there for you but the general and most significant problem in several universities is the lack of qualified faculty, which is a problem that is even more critical than financial issues. You need someone to transfer their

TUBITAK Science Awards

knowledge to you and us at the Turkish Academy of Sciences we are aware of these issues and can see it clearly.

In Turkey, we have both well-established universities like Istanbul University and new ones like Bitlis University. Turkey currently has **208 universities and 81** medical faculties. This is a significant topic of debate in terms of education policy that we're not going to go into now, but simply put, you can't support these many universities because there aren't enough professors. There may be new academics, but they aren't fully qualified yet. For me, this number is too high. We can't train enough professors to support these many universities. This issue is also a financial one. Let's say a student says, "I'm satisfied with my education, but I also want to do research." They then go to the dean for financial support who tells them that they simply don't have the budget for the research. At that point, to get budgeting, you need to go to TÜBİTAK and secure a project with them. This is a path that ultimately limits a researcher and their project proposals might still be rejected. I know of an assistant who, four or five years ago, sold his car to finance his thesis; there is simply not enough money in the system to finance a big research proposal. When you establish so many universities, you have to create the necessary infrastructure needed for the employment of faculty staff, the teaching staff, and the budget that they need. This is beyond us as individuals but it's part of a broader education policy. Koç University is a luxurious university both for students and staff but if you were to step out of that environment and go to another university, say for example Niğde University, you would be surprised by the differences and challenges. It's just that the people there work in a different environment with more challenges and hurdles.

Doruk: As you've mentioned, I've seen this disparity while working at UCLA as well. The people who conduct research here are simply brilliant and are very successfully working at the very top of their fields globally. I don't want to insinuate that their only advantage is monetary, but even the prices of the computers they use and the costs that these labs can sustain are incredibly high. A majority of the universities in Turkey simply can't begin seriously working in certain fields because of the cost of entry.

Yes, you're right. Would you say that the costs are too far out of reach for us? Can't we provide these opportunities in Turkey as well?

Doruk: We can of course, if we were to focus on certain fields and areas but with so many universities with numerous laboratories and projects... it seems almost impossible to establish conditions in every lab that are at a satisfactory base level right now. Maybe if we were to focus on a number of labs and fund them extensively, these conditions could be met.

What you're saying is very important. In previous years, I suggested, and we discussed, taking TÜBİTAK's science center in Gebze as a model for academic research centers in Turkey. Instead of each university incurring expenses and sustaining niche operations individually, I proposed establishing research centers in each of the geographic regions of Turkey. It didn't happen, for reasons I'm not sure

TÜBİTAK: Marmara Research Center

why. We might not be able to provide the same conditions as some American universities across the board, but by establishing scientific centers in places like Bursa or Eskişehir, we can create centralized state-of-the-art facilities accessible to all universities. This is something that can be done.

VIII. WHAT DEVELOPMENTS DO YOU FORESEE IN THE FIELDS OF HEMATOLOGY/IMMUNOLOGY IN THE NEAR FUTURE? ARE THERE ANY PROJECTS YOU'RE FOLLOWING THAT EXCITE YOU?

You're somewhat involved in this topic already. I can mention a few key areas in our field that excite me, though it's hard to rank them. Bioinformatics, which is relevant to both medicine and engineering, is one of them. Biotechnology, specifically the discovery of drugs and the identification and study of molecules that determine our health and diseases, is a rapidly evolving field. In 1953, the DNA in our cells was discovered, and it was awarded the Nobel Prize in 1962. Then, in 2001, the Human Genome Project mapped the human genome from a collaboration between the U.S. and U.K. scientists. These two developments significantly advanced both medicine and engineering, marking a turning point for us. After 2001, a field called Genomic Medicine emerged, which has been advancing in many areas, from drug development to pathobiology and disease treatments.

The stem cell, which is the most fundamental cell, that forms every part of the human body was discovered. These cells, found in utero form the entire structure of the baby and later the human. Now, we can produce these stem cells in laboratories, which has emerged as a new field. It is called induced pluripotent stem cells (iPS Cells). For example, there are high-level studies seeking answers to how organs like the liver, intestines, and brain are formed. Stem cell research has also started and is in good progress at Hacettepe. Alongside this, 3D printing has emerged as a new field, and there is ongoing work on artificial organ production. It hasn't been fully realized yet, but these developments may happen in the next 10-15 years.

There's also the field of neurology, which has long been unresolved, such as with Alzheimer's disease. This topic remains an unsolved mystery. However, important studies on this are being conducted at Koç and Bilkent Universities, as well. I believe there will be significant breakthroughs in this area over the next 15 to 20 years. These fields interest me greatly and are advancing rapidly. I saved cancer for last because, despite many advancements, we still haven't solved it. Cancer will continue to occupy us for a long time; it's a very complex disease. We know certain factors that increase risk, like smoking and UV light but there are other unknown factors as well. Cancer can affect everyone, from infants to adults, making it very difficult to map the entirety of it. Then there's the field of bioinformatics, which engineers are currently working on extensively. And more recently, there's artificial intelligence, a field that has somewhat surpassed my era. I don't want to talk too much about it because I don't fully understand it, but it has very important ethical dimensions. For example, is it ethical to write a research paper using ChatGPT? Is it a fraud? The future of this is quite challenging. Is it ethically correct for doctors to use artificial intelligence? This is being debated. Its use impacts everyone—the patient, the insurance company, the health care provider, and the hospital.

Doruk: There are certain tools developed that aid in the decision-making process of diagnosing diseases. If something were to go wrong, a doctor using AI could rightfully say "I didn't make the decision, the black box did." Who is responsible if an error occurs, the developers, the doctors? Or how will we resolve the legal and ethical problems that arise when we're trying to collect data to train and perfect our models?

I think when you return to Turkey, you should organize a symposium on this topic. Invite professors, faculty members, students, and professionals. It's important that we put these issues out on the table and debate them with experts from different fields and have a rational discussion. We currently need a collective brainstorming session because we're at the very start of the process and we have many problems that need to be solved, or at least reach a consensus on. Thank you for inviting me to this interview and for your kind support and encouragement during the session